

- NIC- 152 - Manufacture of dairy products.
NIC- 153 - Manufacture of grain mill products, starch and starch products and prepared animal feed.
NIC- 154 - Manufacture of other food products

Scope, Data sources and Prices and Period of study

The scope of study is confined to manufacture of food products industry of organised manufacturing sectors of Punjab at three digit level. Major source of data for the study is Annual Survey of Industries (ASI). Various issues of annual survey of industries, www.circonindia.com and statistical abstract of Punjab are used. For making price corrections in the reported data on value of output, gross value added, wholesale price index of manufacture of food industry has been used. Wholesale price index for transport and machinery has been used to adjust the data on fixed capital. Consumer price index has been used to deflate the emoluments. Every deflator has 1993-94 as a base year. This study covers the period of 1980-81 to 2002-03; it has also been divided into two phases, pre-reform period (1980-81 to 1990-91) and post-reform period (1991-92 to 2002-03) to capture the impact of change in policy regimes. Present study has been divided into three sections. In the first section methodology is given. In the second section total factor productivity and its growth rates are explored. In the last section concluding remarks and policy implications are given.

SECTION I

Methodology

We are fully aware of limitations of partial factor productivities, so a more comprehensive measure of productivity is the total factor productivity, which takes into account all factors of production is calculated with the help of translog index.

Translog Index can be calculated as under.

$$\frac{\Delta V_t}{V_t} = \log V_{t+1} - \log V_t = \Delta \log V_t$$

$$\frac{\Delta L_t}{L_t} = \log L_{t+1} - \log L_t = \Delta \log L_t$$

$$\frac{\Delta K_t}{K_t} = \log K_{t+1} - \log K_t = \Delta \log K_t$$

Where V is value added, L- labour employed K – capital

$$\bar{W} = \frac{1}{2}(W_{t+1} + W_t)$$

Where W = Wage = $\frac{\text{Emoluments}}{\text{GrossValueAdded}}$

$$\bar{r}_t = (1 - \bar{w}_t),$$

$$\bar{r}_t = \frac{1}{2}(r_{t+1} + r_t)$$

Now

$$\frac{\Delta A}{A} = \frac{\Delta V_t}{V_t} - \left(\bar{w}_t \frac{\Delta L_t}{L_t} + \bar{r}_t \frac{\Delta K_t}{K_t} \right)$$

Translog Index of total factor productivity

The index for base year, A (0) is taken as 1 then the index for subsequent years is computed using the following equation

$$A_{t+1} = A_t \left(1 + \frac{\Delta A_t}{A_t} \right)$$

SECTION II

Translog Index and Total Factor Productivity Growth: Food Industry

Translog index and total factor productivity (TFP) growth of food industry and at disaggregate level have been shown in table I. In food industry, trend growth rate of total factor productivity is significant (2.41 per cent per annum) and higher in pre-reform period as compared to post-reform period (0.98 per cent per annum). In post-reform period, although trend growth rate is low (0.98 per cent per annum) yet it is significant statistically. Here results vindicate our earlier exercise. In production, processing and preservation of meat, fish, fruit, vegetable, oils and fats (NIC-151), manufacture of grain mill products, starch and starch products (NIC- 153), and manufacture of other food products industry (NIC-154) trend growth rate of total factor productivity (TFP) is higher in pre-reform period as compared to post-reform period, where it turned to be negative. One possible reason may be that new economic policies and technology have adverse impact on food industry and also at disaggregate levels. Dairy product industry is only exception where growth rate of

foreign dimensions of manufacturing sector are largely responsible for the lower growth rate of total factor productivity.

TABLE -I
Translog Index and Growth Rates of Total Factor Productivity of
Food Industry and Its Sub-Groups

YEAR	Production, processing and preservation of fruit, fish, vegetable, meat etc.	Manufacture of dairy products	Manufacture of starch & starch products	Manufacture of other food products	Food industry
1980-81	1	1	1	1	1
1981-82	1.08	1.20	1.12	1.078	1.13
1982-83	1.29	1.38	1.11	1.283	1.27
1983-84	0.99	1.29	1.25	1.595	1.33
1984-85	0.99	1.43	1.13	1.55	1.31
1985-86	1.28	1.36	1.22	1.43	1.35
1986-87	1.23	1.14	1.23	1.21	1.25
1987-88	0.93	1.16	1.32	1.21	1.27
1988-89	1.23	1.30	1.36	1.33	1.40

1989-90	1.26	1.22	1.41	1.23	1.39
1990-91	1.27	1.48	1.23	1.11	1.38
1991-92	1.11	1.56	1.38	1.27	1.46
1992-93	0.99	1.26	1.40	1.35	1.40
1993-94	0.98	1.31	1.42	1.63	1.49
1994-95	0.93	1.21	1.26	1.59	1.39
1995-96	0.96	1.15	1.30	1.48	1.38
1996-97	0.79	1.32	1.41	1.25	1.37
1997-98	0.75	1.42	1.40	1.29	1.40
1998-99	0.66	1.73	1.28	1.22	1.36
1999-2000	0.75	1.78	1.51	1.35	1.54
2000-01	0.88	2.08	1.40	1.24	1.62
2001-02	0.91	2.09	1.31	1.21	1.61
2002-03	0.96	1.90	1.22	1.11	1.53

Trend Growth Rate (TGR)					per
cent per annum					
1980-81 to 1990-91	1.61 (1.38)	1.29 (1.89)	2.53* (4.48)	0.37 (0.25)	2.41* (3.66)
1991-92 to 2002-03	-1.88 (-1.65)	4.65* (4.08)	-0.40 (-0.85)	-2.0* (-2.57)	0.98** (2.11)
1980-81 to 2002-03	-1.71* (-3.71)	2.10* (4.78)	0.95* (3.95)	0.06 (0.16)	1.29* (6.35)

Note: Figures within Brackets are the t- ratios

* 1% level of significance.

** 5 % level of significance

SECTION III

Concluding Remarks and Policy Implications

Growth rate of total factor productivity is positive and significant for the Manufacturing of Food products industry (except manufacture of dairy product industry) in pre-reform period ; however, this momentum could not be maintained in post-reform period, where growth rate either declined or turned to negative. Food industry that has the potential to develop could not grow to their capacity, owing to laxity of government. Total factor productivity evidenced lower numerical value for food industry and all its disaggregate (except manufacturing of dairy product industry) in post-reform period as compared to pre-reform period. It implies fruits of liberalization period are not enjoyed by food industry. More government expenditure should spent on research and development of improvement of total factor productivity. Large sized units, which must based on local raw mateial and must

